

A BLACK BEAD**SAMAN HASHEMIPOUR***

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Her colleague asked her gibingly: “You’re always on the phone. Who’s the new entrant?”

The girl smiled and continued to write on her phone as fast as a scrivener. Everyone in the room was wondering about her new boyfriend. A few weeks ago, after being separated by her lover, she had been hospitalized in sorrow. The doctor diagnosed that discomfort in her stomach is caused by the mood. As I remember, in a psychological anatomy poster, I have seen that love pain causes tummy ache from time to time. I’m not sure if the poster is scientific or not, but that poster attested how the pain of love affects the heart, brain, liver and intestines.

In literature classes at high school, our teacher was describing the stories of Khosrow, Farhad and Shirin in Nezami’s masterpiece, and at the end of each lesson, he was repeating the same sentence with an impish smile at the end; “If you don’t suffer the pain of love, be in love with a cat. Don’t forget to leave the door open to be pinched!” Although the name of the book was *Khosrow and Shirin*, I was calling the poetry, “Farhad and Shirin.” Maybe the reason is that evermore I am against all stors. I enjoyed to call it just like that. Couldn’t figure out the reason but I don’t like ablers. Maybe on that account, I was feeling better. I even started to criticize our sciential school principal referring to the downfall of the Soviet Union and our evolution into a unipolar world. In breaks, when we were playing mad libs with my classmates, I preferred the revolutionary or fairy tales’ characters such as a bandit ROBIN HOOD to a famous athlete or politician. My heroes were defeating powerful figures. Conceivably I didn’t like Khosrow because he was a prince. Under Khosrow’s jealousy, Farhad, my hero, died of his love grief. I didn’t even talk to my friends who took the side of the great Prince of Sassanids, Khosrow. In my opinion, Khosrow had confounded Shirin with his wealth! In the story, Farhad is introduced as a secondary character, which was increasing my reaction towards the poet.

Another colleague asked: “Did you meet him recently?”

“He lives in Venice.”

“Didn’t you see him up close?”

The girl was still messaging. She finished her sentence and hardly said, “We met!”

“You are used to the arms-length relationship! The previous one was also living away. We saw the result!”

She remained unresponsive.

As far as I remember, Shirin fell in love with handsome Khosrow’s picture. Farhad, on the other hand, bridged stones for the comfort of Shirin’s sheep! But, as the old saying goes, the rich man’s joke is always funny.

With her slim smile, she said, “maybe I will settle in Venice next year.”

A colleague was commenting on the spiritual effects of the relationship that was being conducted remotely. Through, I was watching a man from the window who was collecting the falling leaves on the ground with a broom.

Years later, I am still glad that I remember some verses of this book, just because, these days I forget everything. It was pleasing to recall the issue of Khosrow with his rival. By the broom swinging from one side to the other, I remembered Khosrow and Farhad’s discussion: Khosrow asked Farhad, “Where are you from?” Farhad answered, “From a pretty close town.” Then he asked, “What is your occupation?” He responded that they are generally traders; “We buy sorrow and sell lives.” Khosrow replies, “Selling lives is impertinent.” Farhad answered, “But it is an expected way of behaviour by a lover,”. When Khosrow presumes Farhad to hurt to the quick, he answered, “You think I fell in love with my heart, but I fell in love spunkily.” In response to “To what degree are you in love?” Farhad responds, “Shirin is lovely than my dear life.” Khosrow wonders how Farhad is going to cleanse Shirin’s love, and Farhad mentions he will forget Shirin when he is “carried out feet foremost”. I also remember how Farhad gives jealous Khosrow a piece of his mind by declaring he sets his heart on her heart. Khosrow deridingly rounds on by saying, “If she scratches your eye out,” and Farhad in an instant utters, “I put forward the other eye”.

Everyone in the room was talking about the beauties of Venice. Someone said to the girl, “Summertime after you got married, we’ll visit you in Venice” and continued: “Dreamlike. I wonder about the houses built on the river.”

Unintentionally, I caught my eye on the black screen of the girl’s phone. Venice is a cheerless name for me. The city of love always reminds me of the collapse of the merchant’s house in *The Venetian Merchant* or the sinking of the merchant’s ships. I wonder if moving the rich protagonist’s down in the world caused some eyebrows to raise on me, or not? I don’t know.

Albeit I know the play is a comedy, it is imprinted as a tragedy on my brain. I also didn't feel sorry for the bankruptcy of the tradesman.

"It's the matter of destiny. It is fate," she said. "We're just chatting, guys! I'm gonna introduce him to you soon."

"When he comes to visit you?" someone asked. "Actually, I will go to him," the girl answered with a wink. "But only if I find the appropriate plane ticket," he said additively.

In the story of *Khosrow and Shirin*, I wonder how many times did the lovers travel to the other one's homeland? Top all, each took months, and finally, they failed to meet each other.

I don't remember. I forget everything these days.

We were gathered in a colleague's office, and there was playing a Turkish folk song on her laptop: "Extended in root like a waterleaf / Prolonged on neck your beautiful hair."

When I was about to leave my office, we came eye to eye with the girl. I couldn't help her stranded wire hair. Just then, the sunlight shining through her face was brightening her lips. The mark on her lip caught my attention.

Since the morning I went to her room a couple of times wantonly, but I never noticed the pink pimples on her face.

"He has a friendly conversation. You'll like him," she said. When talking, she waived her phone. She was trying to fix the bracelet on her right arm with her left hand. A few days ago, she found that bracelet impressing on my wing. Without thinking, I wear it off at once and gifted to her. Every morning I was pleased to see it in her arm. I wanted to believe that the bracelet was protecting the evil eye beads from her eyes.

Still playing that folk song: "Your name is an angel name. It's a rose garden / Are there others in your heart?" I got up and said, "See you all!" Leaving the room, from a crowd, only the girl said "see ya" when she saw me off. As I passed by the table, the voice of the Turkish folk, sounded the lushest in my ears: "Are you an angel? I don't know / There is no precedent in the world like you".

While walking to my next door office, I reminded the continuation of discussion between *Khosrow and Farhad*. When *Khosrow* asked, "What if you don't reach her?" *Farhad* said, "I'll watch her from afar as she looks at the moon." Even, in answer to the comment that "being away from the moon is not normal to us," *Farhad* commented, "The mad ought to be away from the moon".

-What if she alights on what you got?

- I always want it from God.
- Nobody has regretted patience.
- I don't have the heart to get patience!
- I pity for you because your matter of love is hard.
- But is there anything more beautiful than love?
- Forget Shirin. It's mine.
- Then what should I desperate do?
- What if I chat with Shirin?
- I'll fire the universe by my curse.

I asked by myself, “When cute Shirin was looking out the window, at the time she knew Farhad sacrificed himself for her comfort, was she thinking Khosrow?” As I closed the door of my office, I saw a black evil eye bead on my bracelet, similar to the black eyes of the girl. The folk song's hoarse voice came to my office: “Your eyes are like a light on the horizon / Your eyebrows are as beautiful as a dark cloud.”

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